
ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON LIBRARIES

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Abstract:

The symbiotic relationship between the libraries and social media for the creation of digital environment in the LIS domain. It is noted that 21st century librarianship witnesses huge changes in the field of Library and Information science. As a result of which many changes in the LIS domain have altered the forms of information and nature of services but the basic role of the libraries - to cater the information according to need and demand of the users- is the same. Digital library along with the internet helps the library users to access their necessary resources without physically visiting the library. So it is the high time for the library professionals to think the alternate ways to attract the users and to meet their need and demand. As the popularity of social media are growing exponentially, library professionals cannot keep themselves aside without exploiting the social media. By using social media libraries can attract their users and enable them to participate in the production of library products and services.

Keywords: Face Book, Twitter, Library, Social Networking, Reference Service, YouTube, Flickr, Blog.

Introduction:

A computer based collection of tools, is a platform where people can build social relations among people who share their interests, activities, personal matters, etc. They share their information in different forms, namely text, photos, audio, video, etc. In other words, Social media are a collective term for the online tools and services such as blogs, wikis, social networking sites, photo and video sharing communities, social bookmarking, podcasts, discussion forums, RSS feeds, presentation sharing and a lot more. Over two hundred social networking sites are now available in the world. Due to the popularity of social media, library professional cannot keep themselves aside

from the use of social media in the LIS domain. It is a great challenge for the librarian to capture the attention of the remote users who are using social media like Social news (Dig, Propeller), Social Bookmarking (Del.icio.us, Blink list), Social Networking (Face book, MySpace, LinkedIn), Social Photo and Video Sharing (YouTube, Flickr) and Wikis (See Table One) and who are reluctant to visit the library physically. So many libraries of India and around the world are giving facility to their users to use social media through library's website. By exploiting Social media the library can give extra facility to reach their services to their web users, and offer them to communicate with the library.

Benefits of Using Social Media in Libraries:

- It helps libraries to get closer to the users and build a collaborative platform for the users. Social media are a great way to attract the attention of new users for marketing of library resources and services. Thus Social media creates potential users of the library.
- Registration is very easy for any user. It allows users to update their profile via their mobile phone through text messaging and apps downloaded for certain smart phones and tablets. User can create as many accounts as he wishes to create in different social media.
- Users are able to get answers to specific questions by using social media. It is also helpful to elicit ideas and suggestions. Thus it enhances reference service.
- Library authority can encourage programs and events by rating, reviewing, and sharing with their friends and neighbors. This new method has applied for Amazon and the same may be applied for libraries.
- Through the use of social media, the messages can be sent to others persons or users so that the message can be viewed easily. This is a great attempt for advocating the concept of reading lists generated by librarians, and in some cases user generated reading list which is more beneficial than librarians. • Social media helps students in choosing library resources and making it easy for them to add content to the library's website.
- It is not highly expensive. User can afford benefit of social media by paying phone service provider fees.
- Users are willing to use Social Media in libraries and they showed their urge

towards the benefits of social media in library resources and services.

Purpose of Using the Social Media in Libraries:

1. To attract potential users of the library by making announcements, providing reference service, networking with other libraries, promoting general library services, providing quick updates to users and their query and to develop communities. Users about new arrivals to build discussion groups.
2. Users are to be given links to recommended Internet Resources, Book reviews, latest arrivals, etc.
3. To communicate among the librarians about their professional development.
4. To build an e-reputation of LIS domain.
5. To modernize the library & information Centre.

Social Networking:

MySpace: Here library users can use html to customize their profile and they can add new graphics and videos on it. Face book: -With the help of Face book, library users can be informed with different upcoming events and share the information about their new arrivals and editions of books. Face book mainly helps in marketing of services and products. Photo can be tagged through the use of it. Ask-A – Librarian service can be exploited by using it.

Twitter: Twitter is a free social networking used to send and read messages known as tweets. At present librarians share all kinds of news regarding library through the use of twitter. Librarians can highlight new materials, new groups, meetings and

more with some of these suggestions through twitter.

LinkedIn: It is a professional networking site. It can be used by the librarians to create professional connections and to market library services among other library professionals spread all over the world and can also share their ideas and professional experiences.

WEB 2.0: Ajax: - Ajax, part of web 2.0, is one tool of choice for creating interactive pages with easily changeable components. In libraries web pages can update frequently with new messages with help of Ajax without reloading the entire browser page.

Mashups: It is hybrid of different social media. The users are allowed to edit OPAC data and metadata and create a user driven catalogue.

IM (Instant Messaging): Users can chat with the librarian through IM, an online communication service which is used for reference service and voice chat. Here co-browsing, file sharing, screen capturing and data sharing; etc. are also possible. It is generally communicated through SMS via mobile phone.

YOUTUBE: Libraries can also advocate their different programs, conferences, workshops, seminars, Virtual conferences by uploading their videos on the YouTube.

FLICKR: It is an online image sharing service. Sharing and uploading picture of library events and services are possible for libraries by using Flickr.

RSS: RSS, a collection of web feed formats for publishing frequently updated works, became popular as web users need not to browse frequently the new entry in their preferred website. Feed reader or feed aggregator is

needed to read RSS feed. The popular feed readers are blog lines, Google reader, feed demon, etc. In the domain of LIS, RSS may be used for—

- Marketing the library services among distance learner.
- Dissemination of updated news to the web user
- Selective Dissemination Of Information
- Sending News to the users according to their area of interest
- Library news, events, orientation, etc.

Social Bookmarking and Tagging:

Social bookmarking (see Table Three) is a method for the users of internet to store, organize, search the bookmarks of the web pages on the net with the help of user-driven Libraries can use social bookmarking web sites to tag and develop online catalog of library resources. Delicious is an online social bookmarking service which store and share the large number of web bookmarks. Other notable bookmarking services are CiteUlike, Diigo, Google Reader, folkd, etc.

Role of Librarian While Using Social Media in Libraries:

Due to advent of internet, the librarian of the 21st century, popularly known as — Librarian 2.0, can understand the web users deeply in terms of their goals and aspirations, workflows, social and content needs, and more. Librarian 2.0 is where the user is, when the user is there. For the utilization of social media, a librarian —

- Adopts the new communication mode of choice - telephone, Skype, IM, SMS, texting, email, virtual reference, etc.
- Cannot avoid traditional cataloging and classification and chooses tagging, folksonomies, and user-

driven content descriptions to inform the web users about OPAC as and when necessary.

- Combines e-resources and print formats.
- Connects people with web technology in the LIS domain.
- Connects the web users with subject expert for discussions, conversations
- Uses the latest tools of communication for sharing of information.
- Uses and caters everything from laptops to PDAs to iPods.
- Develops targeted federated search and adopts the open URL standard.
- Embraces non-textual information and graphics, moving images, audio, and video.
- Encourages user driven metadata and user developed content and commentary.
- Learns the power of the Web 2.0 opportunities.
- Plays an active role in online communication by optimizing the available resources from social media.
- Understands the potential in using content sources like the Open Content Alliance, Google Print, and Open World Catalogue.

Opportunity and Implication of Social software in Libraries:

Social software can be taken as big option by the information Centre for proving high and qualitative resource for user 2.0 .However implication of social software may be a difficult part on the part of new professionals but still expertise over it will be given an immense impact to the library .Social software like Wiki, RSS feed, Blogger, Library Thing, Delicious, Elf etc. can be used for information sharing and collaboration among the online community. If you will think for

professional dwindling side where the role of librarian in the current scenario of IT age is question mark, it can be taken as fine tune to utilize web 2.0 technologies in the field of library services.

Conclusion:

A symbiotic relationship between the libraries and social media are needed to present together best of the physical and digital environment to create learning hubs. Symbiotic relationship is a close relationship between two species –library and social media. This relationship is essential. Sometimes it is harmful and sometimes it is beneficial. But the library and social media create a balance for hi-tech digital environment. In the present century social media is a great advantage with enormous tools for libraries to cater their information in a sophisticated manner.

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